

Smart Grids Transmission Network Testbed: Design, Deployment, and Beyond

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This work was supported in part by the Project "The Energy Conversion and Storage," funded by the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, Call Excellent Research under Project CZ.02.01.01/00/22 008/0004617, and in part by the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic under Project TS01030042.

ABSTRACT Our test environment incorporates a unique blend of physical, emulated, and virtualized components, spanning from electrical substations to SCADA systems, thereby offering a versatile platform for testing against cyber threats, facilitating educational programs, and supporting advanced traffic simulation. Motivated by the increasing digitalization of energy networks and the growing risks associated with cybersecurity and crisis management, this work responds to geopolitical situations and a series of attacks on electricity infrastructure, such as in Ukraine between 2015 and 2024. For instance, in 2015 and 2021, major cyberattacks caused power outages in Ukraine and the USA, emphasizing the urgent requirement for robust testing platforms. Key findings from our deployment highlight the testbed's effectiveness in identifying vulnerabilities, enhancing cybersecurity measures, and providing valuable hands-on learning experiences. The integration of such diverse components not only exemplifies a significant step forward in testbed design but also showcases its potential in fostering innovation and security in the power sector. Through detailed comparisons with existing testbeds, we underscore our testbed's distinct features and its contribution to bridging the gap in current methodologies, setting a new benchmark for future developments in smart grid testing and education.

INDEX TERMS Critical energy infrastructure, education, security, testbed.

I. INTRODUCTION

AT A TIME when concepts such as Energy 4.0 and Smart Grids associated with digitalization are becoming central to the energy sector, new technologies must be developed and tested to optimize systems and ensure cyber security [1]. The importance of test platforms, or testbeds, can be demonstrated through real-world cases. For instance, in 2015, Ukraine's energy sector lost power supply due to a cyberattack targeting the SCADA systems of distribution networks [2]. A similar incident occurred in the United States in 2021 when the Colonial Pipeline faced cyberattacks, leading to massive supply disruptions [3]. In such cases, testbeds can play a crucial role, as they allow for safe experimentation with cyber threats and the development of mitigation strategies without risking real systems.

Beyond cybersecurity, testbeds are also essential for simulating common and extraordinary operational scenarios

that can lead to network overloads or outages. For example, in February 2021, Texas experienced massive power outages caused by a wave of extreme cold [4]. This situation led to a sudden increase in power demand due to heightened heating needs, while parts of the energy infrastructure, including wind turbines and gas plants, ceased functioning due to freezing. This caused critical grid overload and subsequent planned shutdowns. Test platforms enable the simulation of such crisis scenarios, including sudden overloads and outages, to examine system responses under extreme loads. Thanks to these simulations, energy companies can develop and optimize emergency plans and response strategies, such as controlled disconnection of lower-priority consumption sites, without the need to interfere with real infrastructure.

The extraction of data from existing systems is crucial for successful research and development of new technologies in the energy sector. However, these data, essential for

innovation and progress, are often sensitive and virtually unavailable for critical energy infrastructure [5]. Even testing in real-world conditions is, in most cases, very complicated and sometimes unrealistic. The risk of long-term power outages caused by testing processes or poor equipment development involves potential danger to the lives and health of end users [6].

Testbeds play a crucial role in simulation and testing and can provide a platform for hands-on education [7]. Testbeds enable safe experimentation without compromising existing systems. Simulation of near-realistic scenarios in testbeds contributes to a better understanding of the systems themselves, potential threats, and the development of effective strategies to mitigate them. Testbeds must provide sufficient complexity and realism for practical use, which entails many challenges. The energy sector, especially transmission and distribution networks, is associated with sensitive data and critical assets [8]. For this reason, great emphasis is placed on data security. Real-life tests carry the risk of operational failures that can cause power interruptions and other adverse impacts.

Therefore, this paper focuses on testbeds in the power industry, focusing on the transmission and distribution parts, where a comprehensive analysis of the utility parameters of current testbeds and their approaches to the problem is performed. The analysis focuses on implementation, communication protocols used, and the use of testbeds. Furthermore, the paper presents its unique testbed, including its technical description, experience, testing, and use in simulation/emulation, testing and education. The benefits of the implemented testbed compared to others are its modularity, scalability and extensibility. By combining virtualization/simulation, emulation and physical components, the testbed is capable of creating complex scenarios for cyber incidents, data generation or training. Based on these strengths, open-source policy is able to respond to emerging technologies, protocols and standards.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The energy sector is undergoing a digital transformation defined by concepts such as Energy 5.0, artificial intelligence, edge computing and new communication protocols. These technologies are increasing the efficiency of networks, but also their complexity, placing new demands on virtualization, simulation and emulation, which are key to identifying and testing security measures. Testbeds play a crucial role not only as platforms for development and testing, but also for training professionals. However, to remain relevant in a rapidly changing environment, they must be flexible and adaptable. However, current testbeds often suffer from poor interoperability and limited protocol support. They are further limited by the high cost of proprietary hardware and their focus on narrow application domains, which restricts their use for a wider range of problems. Table 1 lists the

relative testbeds selected according to the criteria¹ in IEEE, where the year was specified as 2015-2022. The search by year was limited because the paper [9] summarizes the most suitable legacy testbeds up to this year. A total of 130 results were returned, of which testbeds focused on the energy sector were selected.

The table is divided into seven parts, where most of the columns are expressed by ✓ or ✗. These values indicate whether the column is represented in the testbed or not. The first column of the table (References) is the identifier for the testbed and is represented by a citation to the article from which the testbed information was obtained. The second column (Year) refers to the year of the article.

The columns collectively labeled Realization indicate whether the testbed consists of virtualized/simulated, emulated, or physical components. A virtual/simulation system or element is a software program that enables the virtualization of individual elements or entire systems. This approach is not tied to a specific hardware or operating system. Specifically, it may be, for example, OPNET Modeler or NS-3.

An emulated element or system is a software toolset that produces the same inputs and outputs on HW as a real physical element or system. However, an emulated system or element is not dependent on a specific HW; it only depends on replicating physical inputs and outputs that match the physical real element or system. Specifically, this could be the implementation of libraries for the IEC 61850 standard on a Raspberry Pi with modules for sensing electrical signals that would be converted to data communication and thus emulate, for example, a Protection Unit device.

A physical system or element is a real device commonly used for real-world applications. Alternatively, a physical system or element is a device that replicates the inputs and outputs of real devices but is proprietary to HW, SW, or both and is not portable to other HW or SW. An example would be an RTDS that has the ability to simulate large networks, emulate devices for physical outputs, and have proprietary HW. In this case, it is classified as a physical element since, like real devices, it is a device with dedicated HW and SW, even though it meets the parameters for virtualization/simulation.

This distribution was defined based on the benefits of each system/item. Virtual systems have the advantage of simplicity. They depend only on the performance of the HW used, their setup possibilities, and the resulting simulation [10]. Their disadvantage is usually their low extensibility (e.g., OPNET Modeler) and high complexity (e.g., NS-3) when new components, such as new protocols, need to be implemented [11]. Another disadvantage is the resulting plausibility of the simulated data. Unlike emulated or physical systems, real data is much harder to achieve with virtualized systems [12]. Virtualized systems can simulate

¹(ics OR scada OR ied OR substation) AND (testbed OR test bed OR cyber range OR cyber-range) AND (virtual* OR simulat* OR emulat* OR virtual machine OR physic*) AND (electric* OR energy OR 61850 OR 60870 OR DNP3)

TABLE 1. Electrical power energy testbeds.

References	Year	Realization			Protocols						Elements					Purpose			Other	
		virt./simul.	emulated	physical	IEC61850	IEC60870	DNP3	OPC UA	ModBusTCP	other	SCADA	HMI	(MR/TU)	C/IED	S/IED	Attacker	gen./simul.	education		security
[16]	2010	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	-	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	HIL
[17]	2011	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	✓	M	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	RTDS
[18]	2013	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	-
[19]	2015	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	✓	X	-	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	RTDS, Python
[20]	2015	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	✓	RTDS, OpenPLC61850
[21]	2015	✓	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	C	X	✓	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓	RTDS, IEEE 14, NS-3
[22]	2015	✓	X	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	-	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	PSAT
[23]	2015	✓	X	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	C	✓	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X	✓	OPAL-RT, Mat-lab/Simulink, RTDS, HIL
[24]	2015	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	-	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	SNORT, BRO
[25]	2016	✓	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	-
[26]	2016	✓	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	C	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	NS-3 , Riverbed Modeler, OpenPDC
[27]	2016	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	libiec61850, IEDscout
[28]	2016	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	Matlab/simulink, libiec61850
[29]	2016	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	X	✓	-	✓	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X	✓	RTDS, Matlab
[30]	2016	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	C	✓	X	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	✓	Matlab, Python, HIL/SIL, RTDS, OpenPDC
[31]	2016	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	-
[32]	2018	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	P	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	IDS
[33]	2018	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	-
[34]	2018	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	libiec61850, GNS3, Matlab/Simulink
[35]	2018	✓	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	✓	VirtualBox
[36]	2018	✓	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	RTDS
[37]	2018	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	X	C	X	X	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	RTDS, IEEE 14-bus
[38]	2018	✓	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X	-	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	✓	✓	-
[39]	2019	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	RTDS
[40]	2019	X	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	M	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	IRIG-B, EthernetIP, NTP
[41]	2019	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	-	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	qtester104,OpenMUC
[42]	2019	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	C	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	RTDS
[43]	2020	✓	X	X	X	X	✓	X	X	-	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	PWDS
[44]	2020	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	-
[45]	2020	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	-	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	IEEE 14-bus, OPAL-RT
[46]	2020	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	IEEE 39-bus
[47]	2020	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	I	✓	X	X	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	RTDS, OpenADR 2.0
[48]	2021	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	X	C	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	PWDS, RTAC
[49]	2021	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	-
[50]	2021	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	RTDS
[51]	2021	✓	X	X	X	X	✓	X	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	IEC62443, NIST800-82, Ethernet/IP
[52]	2021	X	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	X	-	✓	X	X	✓	✓	X	✓	X	✓	Microgrid
[53]	2022	✓	X	X	✓	X	✓	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	-
[54]	2022	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	✓	✓	X	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	GNS3
[55]	2022	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	X	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	PWDS, RTAC
[56]	2022	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	-	✓	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	✓	-
[57]	2022	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	✓	-	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	OPAL-RT, Matlab/Simulink, Kali
B	2024	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	libiec61850, lib60870, OpenMUC

B - BUTENET, **M** - ModBusRTU; **C** - C37.118; **I** - IEEE 2030.5; **P** - ICCP; **RTDS** (Real Time Digital Simulator) - Real-time simulation of power networks; **Python** - Programming language; **OpenADR2.0** - Standard for communication between electricity providers and their customers; **libiec61850** - Open-source IEC 61850 library; **lib60870** - Open-source IEC 60870 library; **GNS3** - Graphical network designer and simulator; **Matlab/Simulink** - Computing and simulation environment; **IRIG-B** - Time coding standard used in power systems; **EthernetIP** - Industrial Ethernet communication protocol; **NTP** (Network Time Protocol) - Time synchronization protocol; **RTAC** (Real-time Automation Controller) - Controller used in power systems; **Microgrid** - A small power grid with the ability to operate independently or in parallel with the main power grid; **PSAT** (Power System Analysis Toolbox) - Power system analysis tool; **qtester104** - IEC 60870-5-104 testing tool; **OpenMUC** - Open-source SCADA with a range of protocols; **IEEE 39-bus** - Electrical test network model with 39 nodes for simulations; **IEC 62443** - Standard for cybersecurity of industrial control systems; **NIST 800-82** - Cybersecurity Guide for Industrial Control Systems; **IEEE 14-bus** - Electrical test network model with 14 nodes for simulations; **OPAL-RT** - Hardware for simulation and testing in the power industry; **Kali** - Linux distribution for penetration testing and forensics; **NS-3** - Data network simulator; **Riverbed Modeler** - Software tool for modeling, simulation and analysis of communication networks; **OpenPDC** - Phasor Data Concentrator for working with phasor meter data in power networks; **HIL** (Hardware In the Loop) - Hardware integrated into simulations; **RSCAD** - Software tool for simulation of electrical systems; **SNORT** - System for detection and prevention of intrusions in computer networks; **BRO** - Security platform for network traffic analysis; **VirtualBox** - Software for OS virtualization; **IDS** (Intrusion Detection System) - Monitors network traffic and alerts on suspicious activities; **IEDscout** - A tool for dealing with IEDs in power networks; **SIL** (Software In the Loop) Software testing in a simulated environment; **PWDS** (PowerWorld Dynamic Studio) - A software tool for simulating and analyzing the dynamic behavior of power systems.

predefined scenarios using randomized algorithms, even with different outputs, but often do not allow real-time simulations and interventions on scenarios during runtime. Emulated systems/elements are much more accurate in their representation of reality than virtualized ones due to their physical inputs and outputs. Thus, the system/element can respond to unexpected stimuli in many ways and does not have to depend on a pre-prepared scenario [13]. Also, due to physical inputs and outputs, the generated data is closer to realistic due to the need to use real resources. However, they

also have shortcomings. For example, emulating large-scale networks with all physical inputs and outputs will always be very expensive, both in terms of time in implementation and financially [12]. Physical systems/elements, whether real physical devices or purpose-specific systems, could be more precise in representing reality [14]. However, these are usually expensive devices or, in the case of large-scale network implementations, space-intensive [15]. Thus, these are smaller testbeds, but they can faithfully mirror real systems/elements.

The next part of the table, labeled Protocols, contains information on whether the power sector's selected communication protocols (IEC 61850, IEC 60870, DNP3, OPC UA, Modbus TCP) are present in the given test environment. There is also an Other column where communication protocols that were not central to the definition of the table but are essential for the energy sector are summarized.

Next parts of the table are Elements, which include the various communication elements from the electrical substation to the SCADA monitoring center. S/IED and C/IED are the Server or Client stations within the electrical substation. In some testbeds, it is called an IED (Intelligent Electronic Device). (M/R)TU refers to the edge unit that communicates from the electrical substation to the parent SCADA monitoring center that also communicates within the substation, it is called an Master or Remote terminal Unit. HMI (Human Machine Interface) refers to the interface for local control and power station monitoring. In addition to these elements, an Attacker denotes a station or interface that allows various attacks to be simulated in a given test environment at the data communication or power interface level. Each of these elements is an integral part of the power grid, where it represents a certain pattern of data communication and possibilities for scenarios, either from the user's or the attacker's perspective.

The last part of the table is an indication of the use of the test environment. This section has been divided by the data generator or simulator, from a data network communication or energy data perspective. Educational focus for teaching and training in the automated energy sector from the power station to the monitoring centre. Security, which is for simulation and testing in cyber or energy security. Due to the variability of all testbeds, an Other column was defined in the table to include important elements of the testbeds. However, it was not central to the implementation of the table.

PowerCyber CPS [16], developed at Iowa State University (ISU), is a hybrid testbed for cyber-physical security experiments in smart grid. Key features include a combination of physical devices, emulated components, and real-time simulators for hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) experiments. It includes Siemens SCADA, protective relays, SEL 421 phase measurement units (PMUs), and a phase data concentrator (PDC) with communication using DNP3, IEC 61850, and IEEE C37.118 protocols. Heavy reliance on proprietary technologies such as Siemens SCADA systems increases costs and limits flexibility. Expensive physical components limit scalability and complicate parallel operation of experiments, reducing platform efficiency. Limited flexibility in configuring physical components and reliance on predefined templates limits customization. Increasing open-source support and automation could make Testbed more accessible and efficient.

The development of a testing environment at Mississippi State University to study and teach SCADA system cybersecurity is described in [17]. The testbed for cybersecurity of

industrial control systems, including real physical processes, commercial hardware and software, and support for Modbus and DNP3 protocols. The testbed enables simulations of industrial processes such as water towers, gas pipelines or smart grids, and supports research and education. Although it is flexible due to its ability to be programmed in ladder logic and C, its dependence on proprietary elements limits openness and modularity. The lack of open-source components complicates adaptation and extension for broader research purposes and increases implementation and maintenance costs.

A testbed composed of physical, emulated, and simulated components, including virtualized elements using OPNET Modeler, is described in [18]. The testbed includes IT and OT networks with SCADA units, HMI, RTU, and IED, communicating through Modbus/TCP, DNP3, and IEC 60870 protocols. However, differing component requirements and reliance on proprietary software complicate management and reduce modularity; limited emulation and the absence of open-source elements restrict flexibility and adaptation potential for broader research.

VSCADA, a software testing environment for modelling and simulating energy systems, utilizing the OPC UA protocol for communication between the SCADA server and HMI and Python for scenario simulation, is described in [19]. Virtualization enables the connection of physical components; the authors plan integration with RTDS or OPAL-RT for greater accuracy. However, the absence of physical elements and reliance on proprietary iFIX software from General Electric limit realistic event responses and interoperability with broader standards such as Modbus and DNP3, reducing VSCADA's usability for detailed SCADA system resilience testing.

A cyber-physical testbed for vulnerability analysis in smart grids based on the IEC 61850 standard, which combines physical components such as the Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) and power plant emulation, is described in [20]. Support for GOOSE, SV, and MMS protocols enables the simulation of cyber attacks such as DoS, MITM, and ARP spoofing, which helps analyze impacts on SCADA systems. For communication with the SCADA monitoring centre, the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol is used. However, high costs and reliance on specific hardware limit the testbed's scalability and availability for smaller teams, reducing its flexibility and potential for broader research.

A cyber-physical testing environment using RTDS and NS-3 to simulate cyber-physical attacks on smart grids is described in [21]. The testbed combines simulation with real power network elements, with the communication network simulated using NS-3 and utilizing SEL IED units according to IEC 61850, DNP3, and IEEE 37.118 standards. Reliance on proprietary RTDS limits expandability and increases maintenance costs, while integrating NS-3 with RTDS complicates the simulation of scenarios requiring close coordination of physical and virtual components. The need for more support for protocols such as IEC 60870 or

Modbus further limits the testbed's use for research across various industry standards.

A testing environment simulating a SCADA energy system using simulated devices such as RTU, MTU, and HMI and the IEC 60870-5-101 and DNP3 protocols is described in [22]. The absence of real physical components limits the ability to accurately model the physical impacts of cyber attacks and expand to additional standards like IEC 61850. Dependence on proprietary software, specifically the GE/Fanuc iFix HMI system, also limits the testbed's openness. The testing environment can be classified as a simulator for a larger power plant with scalability options depending on available hardware.

A testbed utilizing HIL technology with real phasor measurement units (PMUs) and Opal-RT simulators, which enhances the accuracy of physical simulations, is described in [23]. This setup increases costs and limits scalability due to reliance on specific hardware. Dependence on the proprietary OSIsoft PI-System platform for data management reduces flexibility and openness for integrating other standards. Limited support for protocols such as IEC 60870 or IEC 61850 restricts the testbed's use in various SCADA scenarios, and overall reliance on proprietary components decreases the possibility of replication and sharing results in the research environment.

A cybersecurity testing facility for critical infrastructure in the energy sector, using actual IEDs and RTUs from Elkomtech with values generated in LabView, is described in [24]. Communication is based on IEC 61850 and IEC 60870-5-104 standards and is monitored by Snort and Bro IPS/IDS systems, enabling realistic cyber threat testing. However, reliance on proprietary components limits flexibility and portability, complicating expansion with additional elements and protocols and restricting broader applications beyond the energy sector.

A testbed focused on studying cybersecurity risks and their mitigation in power plant automation according to the IEC 61850 standard is described in [25]. This testbed is part of the G-ICS (GreEn-ER1 Industrial Control Systems Sandbox) platform and combines real IEDs, RTDS power grid simulation, and NS-3 communication network simulation, allowing for cyber attack simulations on the GOOSE protocol. Reliance on physical components increases testing accuracy but also costs and limits flexibility; the testbed is specialized for IEC 61850 and is not easily adaptable to other standards or SCADA applications. The proprietary nature of some IEDs and security tools reduces the platform's openness, limiting its use in a broader research environment and complicating result sharing outside the specific context of power automation, according to IEC 61850.

A testbed for smart grid applications that uses the Riverbed Modeler to emulate the communication network with precise modelling of delays and outages and includes physical elements such as IEDs and Phasor Data Concentrators (PDCs) is described in [26]. PMU communication occurs via IEEE 37.118, enabling monitoring and control of smart grids with

real data collection. However, reliance on specific software, including openPDC, limits the testbed's modularity and flexibility, making integrating additional protocols beyond the smart grid domain difficult and reducing openness for result sharing with other critical infrastructure platforms.

An experimental testbed for digital substations according to IEC 61850, based on open-source tools such as IEDScout and libiec61850, which enables the emulation of communication using GOOSE, SV, and MMS protocols, is described in [27]. The testbed focuses on simulating communication flows, but the absence of physical components limits the possibilities for more complex scenarios involving physical system responses. The platform's extensibility is restricted by its reliance on specific software tools, and proprietary tools reduce its openness and adaptability for broader use beyond the context of digital substations.

The testbed for examining cyber vulnerabilities in data networks within substation environments, which utilizes IEC 61850 and the GOOSE, SV, and MMS protocols for communication, is described in [28]. This testbed functions as a substation-level emulator and allows for the simulation of cyber incidents, with plans by the authors to expand with real IEDs, SCADA, and cyber threat simulations to analyze impacts. The absence of physical components limits the realistic modelling of physical responses to attacks, and the focus on IEC 61850 reduces extensibility for other standards. Openness is further limited by specialized tools that are only partially open-source, complicating adaptation and platform sharing for broader research.

The testbed for control and communication in microgrids, utilizing HIL (Hardware in the Loop) with RTDS for realistic modelling, is described in [29]. The platform includes CompactRIO controllers, EMS in MATLAB, and SCADA in LabView, focusing on closed-loop testing with Modbus TCP protocol support. Dependency on RTDS increases system cost and complexity, and specialization in microgrids limits flexibility and extensibility for other energy systems. Proprietary components reduce the platform's openness, complicating adaptation and sharing of results beyond the microgrid domain.

The testbed for simulating Wide Area Measurement Systems (WAMS) focused on cybersecurity and data mining, utilizing RTDS and HIL for modelling cyber-attacks and events, is described in [30]. The testbed supports IEEE C37.118 and Modbus as primary protocols, with DNP3 and IEC 61850 for specific configurations, allowing the simulation of various power system sizes without hardware changes. Proprietary tools reduce the platform's openness and complicate result sharing and adaptation for broader applications beyond WAMS.

The testbed for the operation, control, and protection of microgrids according to the IEC 61850 standard, which uses RT-LAB along with physical components such as wind energy simulators and a battery energy storage system (BESS), is presented in [31]. Support for MMS, GOOSE, and SV protocols promotes interoperability and enables

plant-level simulation with scalability. However, the focus on IEC 61850 limits flexibility for other standards beyond microgrids, and the use of specific tools like RT-LAB reduces the platform's openness for broader adaptation.

The testbed focused on cybersecurity testing in industrial IoT systems and SCADA/ICS, which includes components such as IED, HMI, RTU, SCADA, and EMS emulated on desktop computers, is described in [32]. Communication uses protocols like DNP3, IEC 61850, MMS, GOOSE, and ICCP/TASE.2, enabling detailed cyber-attack simulations and testing IDS detection capabilities against various threats. IDS and firewalls ensure security; however, reliance on proprietary elements limits the platform's flexibility and openness for broader research and industrial applications.

The EPIC (Electrical Power and Intelligent Control) testbed, focused on research and training in the cyber-physical security of electrical grids, is described in [33]. EPIC includes physical components simulating generation, transmission, microgrids, and smart homes, with communication via protocols such as Modbus, IEC 61850, GOOSE, and MMS, enabling realistic testing. The physical part includes generators, photovoltaic panels, and batteries controlled by PLCs connected to SCADA. However, reliance on proprietary elements reduces openness and complicates result sharing for broader research applications. EPIC is available for rental for research purposes.

The software testbed focused on cybersecurity research in substations according to the IEC 61850 standard is described in [34]. The testbed utilizes open-source tools for protocol manipulation, network communication, and power system simulation, facilitating adaptation and result sharing. It supports IEC 61850 protocols, specifically MMS and GOOSE, but the absence of physical components limits the accuracy of simulations regarding the real impact of cyber-attacks. Specialization in IEC 61850 reduces flexibility for broader industrial applications, and a monitoring system is not included.

The open-source framework for creating and managing SCADA testing environments with support for IEC 60870-5-104 and OPC-UA protocols, with the possibility of extending to Modbus and IEC 61850, is presented in [35]. The platform utilizes Oracle VirtualBox for node configuration and simulates data communication between industrial devices such as HMI and RTU. It focuses on flexibility and scalability, but standardized libraries for common protocols limit simulation accuracy and interoperability with physical elements. Containerization support improves extensibility, though manual configuration and dependency on specific virtualization software reduce portability and complicate setup.

The testbed focused on cyber-resilient protection and control of digital substations according to the IEC 61850 standard, which uses physical ABB protection devices and simulated network elements, is described in [36]. The testbed provides advanced cyber-attack mitigation capabilities through layered cyber-physical security methods based

on protection coordination. However, reliance on commercial relays and RTDS for real-time simulation increases costs and limits accessibility. Detection algorithms have limited adaptability to new attacks and require regular updates, which may reduce sustainability and flexibility.

The testbed focused on distributed monitoring and control with support for decentralized architecture through the DRAS (Distributed Remedial Action Scheme) algorithm on the RIAPS platform and hardware PMU units is described in [37]. The testbed uses proprietary equipment, such as RTDS and Cisco Fog routers, which increases costs and limits portability. The lack of full support for open standards and libraries restricts flexibility for expansion and integration with other systems. The testbed enables testing of cyber failures in a decentralized network, but reliance on specific hardware limits its universal use for broader research.

The RICS-el testbed, designed for research and training in SCADA security and utilizing virtualized components within the Cyber Range And Training Environment (CRATE) of the Swedish Defense Research Agency (FOI), is described in [38]. The testbed includes an OT network with three RTUs communicating via IEC 60870-5-104 and a 400 kV backbone emulator with twenty substations, while the IT network includes robots simulating email, Web, and documents. Although it offers robust capabilities for simulating cyber-attacks, reliance on a proprietary SCADA system and lack of support for open-source platforms reduce accessibility and extensibility for independent research.

The testbed for simulation and automatic testing of protective relays in substations using RTDS, which enables efficient testing and verification of device reliability in real-time, is described in [39]. This testbed allows the simulation of various states and faults and supports online setting adjustments during dynamic situations. However, heavy reliance on proprietary RTDS hardware increases costs and limits availability and extensibility for broader research. The testbed also restricts interoperability due to the lack of open standards and broader protocol support beyond IEC 61850.

The testbed focused on evaluating the vulnerability of critical infrastructure, which emulates a distribution grid substation supported by industrial PLCs, relays, and SCADA systems, is described in [40]. The testbed supports communication according to IEC 61850 and is divided into four levels, enabling the simulation of various protocols and focusing on controlling distributed energy resources and microgrids. Heavy reliance on proprietary hardware and software increases costs and limits portability, while limited support for open protocols reduces interoperability and adaptability for research outside partner institutions.

The security of SCADA systems with the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol and the security threats such as MiTM and DoS attacks resulting from the lack of authentication and encryption are the subject of document [41]. The testbed utilizes open-source tools like OpenMUC but relies on proprietary elements, limiting compatibility and extensibility

for other protocols and standards. The author proposes a threat model based on Petri nets and emulates four types of cyber-attacks, with risk assessment via the AlienVault model identifying unauthorized access and DoS as the most critical threats. Future work includes developing an anomaly detection system for IEC 60870-5-104 integrated into OSSIM.

The ISAAC (Idaho CPS Smart Grid Cybersecurity Testbed) testbed, focused on the cybersecurity of SCADA systems in smart grids with support for IEC 61850 and DNP3 protocols, is described in [42]. This distributed and reconfigurable testbed simulates a realistic energy infrastructure using RTDS, to which IEDs are connected via analogue and digital interfaces. ISAAC provides tools for developing and testing integrated cybersecurity solutions and supports simulations from the process level to the monitoring centre. However, dependence on proprietary RTDS hardware limits the platform's flexibility and portability for broader academic and research use.

The EMP testbed, designed for simulating energy system control using SCADA and EMS with DNP3 protocol support for transmitting network data to EMS software, is described in [43]. Using PowerWorld Dynamic Studio for simulation, this testbed focuses on dispatcher training in energy management rather than complex data communication. Commercial software limits the platform's openness, and the lack of hardware components reduces the potential for realistic simulations and testing of interactions with actual devices, which limits extensibility for other standards, such as IEC 61850.

The testbed focused on teaching digital substation control according to the IEC 61850 standard, which includes load emulation, medium-voltage generators, and a control system with physical devices, is presented in [44]. The testbed enables instruction in setting and configuring protective relays using the GOOSE protocol and XML semantics. However, reliance on Schneider Electric's proprietary software limits flexibility and extensibility for other industrial standards, reducing compatibility with various devices.

The cyber-physical testbed focused on the cybersecurity of power grids, which includes EMS, communication networks, and a physical power system simulator, is described in [45]. The testbed supports DNP3 and IEC 61850 protocols, with power plant simulation realized using OPAL-RT and communication via MMS, GOOSE, and SV. However, it enables realistic simulations with transmission delays and strong dependence on specific hardware and software, which limits flexibility and openness for broader research applications.

The testbed focused on attack detection in substations with IEC 61850 through distributed IDS, which identifies false data before it reaches the control centre, thereby enhancing security, is described in [46]. The testbed includes physical and simulated parts, including RTDS connected to protective devices, a communication gateway, and power amplifiers, allowing the detection of false values in MMS

messages. Although it provides realistic simulations, it relies on proprietary software and limited protocol support, reducing its interoperability and extensibility for broader research purposes.

The cyber-physical testbed for distributed energy resources (DER) security using RTDS and OPAL-RT, which allows high-fidelity monitoring and control of DER, is described in [47]. The testbed supports IEEE 2030.5, IEC 61850, DNP3, and Modbus TCP protocols, enabling realistic simulations with real physical and emulated elements. However, strong reliance on specific hardware increases costs and limits portability and compatibility with other standards, reducing the testbed's extensibility for broader research purposes.

The testbed using PowerWorld Dynamic Studio (PWDS) for real-time simulation of electrical grids, integrated with a cyber-physical environment supporting the DNP3 protocol, is described in [48]. The testbed includes an SEL RTAC hardware platform for automation and control, enabling realistic monitoring and control of power systems and modelling their dynamic behaviour. However, strong reliance on the DNP3 protocol and commercial tools limits compatibility with other protocols and reduces accessibility and extensibility for academic purposes.

The IEC 61850-based testbed, which uses software-defined networking (SDN) for resilience against cyber-attacks, particularly in Substation Automation Systems (SAS), is presented in [49]. After attacks, it allows dynamic network reconfiguration by isolating compromised sections. The testbed simulates a substation with virtualized network infrastructure in a Mininet environment and uses an SDN controller with RECOVERY extension for centralized control. Dependence on proprietary SDN components and only the IEC 61850 protocol limits extensibility and modularity, reducing potential integration with other standards and broader academic use.

The testbed for digital substations, which uses multi-vendor IEDs supporting interoperability via the IEC 61850 protocol, is described in [50]. The testbed is designed to analyze the impact of faulty components in the data communication network and fault states in the power network. It uses RTDS and includes four test models (Swansea North, Whitson/Seabank, Swansea North, and Rassau) focused on the power component. Dependence on proprietary IED components and restriction to the IEC 61850 protocol reduces the testbed's extensibility, modularity, and flexibility for broader research use.

The design of an open-source virtual testbed focused on ICS cybersecurity, intended for simulating cyber vulnerabilities, is presented in [51]. The testbed supports standards such as IEC 62443 and NIST SP 800-82 and protocols Modbus/TCP and DNP3, with its purpose being education and skill development in ICS cybersecurity. The lack of physical components and limited modularity restrict its applicability for more complex industrial scenarios and compatibility with broader standards, such as IEC 61850,

making it primarily suitable for research and educational purposes.

The testbed focused on the IEC 61850 protocol, utilizing emulated IED elements in the Typhoon HIL environment, which provides tools for simulating power electronics and systems, is described in [52]. The testbed focuses on emulating IED units with protective relays, measuring units, circuit breakers, and communication via the GOOSE protocol. The lack of physical components limits realistic responses to dynamic scenarios, and reliance on the IEC 61850 protocol reduces compatibility with other standards, such as DNP3 and IEC 60870, which limits the possibilities for broader research purposes.

The testbed based on the open-source library OpenPLC61850 for studying cyber-attacks in substations enables simulation and hardware implementation on devices such as Raspberry Pi, Arduino, and ESP8266, is presented in [53]. The testbed supports Modbus, DNP3, and MMS protocols from the IEC 61850 standard, allowing communication simulation between IED, HMI, and SCADA. Exclusive focus on IEC 61850 limits compatibility with other protocols, such as IEC 60870, and the lack of physical elements and modularity reduces customization options for broader research use.

The testbed for cybersecurity in electrical substations, which utilizes GNS3 and OPNET for simulation with physical ABB protection devices and emulated components on Raspberry Pi, is described in [54]. Communication is conducted via the GOOSE protocol from the IEC 61850 standard, allowing for the modelling of cyber-attacks within the local network. The focus on the GOOSE protocol limits compatibility with other standards, such as DNP3 and Modbus, and the lack of open-source components and limited modularity reduces the testbed's flexibility for broader research purposes.

The RESLab testbed, focused on cybersecurity in power grids, which utilizes physical, simulated, and emulated components and supports the DNP3 protocol, is described in [55]. The environment includes RTAC, PWDS, a CORE emulator, and a 3-layer switch, providing flexibility for testing various scenarios. The absence of the IEC 61850 protocol limits compatibility with modern standards, and the use of proprietary controllers complicates extensibility for broader research purposes. Additionally, the lack of open-source components reduces the customization and expansion options of the platform for academic use.

The development of a HIL testbed for analyzing vulnerabilities and impacts of the IEC 61850 communication standard in smart grids, utilizing GOOSE, SV, and MMS protocols, is described in [56]. The testbed combines physical and emulated IED elements, enabling detailed cybersecurity and performance analysis, including measurements of protocol delay and accuracy. However, reliance on proprietary HIL devices increases costs and limits flexibility and modularity, while the lack of open-source components reduces accessibility and customization options for academic purposes.

The testbed for modelling APT attacks on power transformer diagnostics (PTDS), which uses physical and emulated components to enable realistic scenarios for testing cyber-attacks, is described in [57]. The testbed supports the IEC 61850 protocol, which limits compatibility with other standards, such as DNP3. Dependence on proprietary elements without support for open-source tools reduces modularity and extensibility for additional research purposes, while the focus on APT attacks limits its versatility for other types of threats.

We found several findings in our analysis of the articles and associated data. Regarding the implementation of the environment, virtualized/simulated was included in 31 cases, while emulated and physical were mentioned in 18 and 29 articles, respectively. In 24 cases, the environment consisted of two or all three environments. This provides more variability in the implementation of different scenarios, e.g., in the generation or simulation of actual data, the connection of physical actual elements, or modularity in case the test environment needs to be extended.

In the area of communication protocols, IEC61850 was the most frequently mentioned standard (28 mentions), followed by other protocols such as DNP3 (17 occurrences), IEC 60870 and Modbus TCP in 8 occurrences, OPC UA (3 occurrences) and other protocols such as C37.118 and IEEE 2030.5, ICCP or Modbus RTU. The IEC 61850 standard is increasingly used within smart electrical substations between IED and MTU/RTU elements, for which it would be used primarily. The three protocols most commonly used here are MMS, GOOSE and SV. The DNP3 protocol is a reasonably modular protocol that is used in both the power and industrial sectors for communication between the IED and SCADA elements. Similar to IEC 60870 is the IEC 60870 standard, which has four main protocols, with IEC 60870-5-104 being the most common protocol for network communication today. This protocol is primarily used for communication between MTU/RTU and SCADA. Modbus TCP and UPC UA are less widespread but still present in the power sector. OPC UA is mainly used for its modularity for communication between MTU or RTU and SCADA when translating different protocols, especially in cases where multiple protocols are represented. Modbus TCP is mainly not used for primary communication and transmission of power data, but mainly represents control of additional elements/systems connected to or in interaction with the power system. In some test environments, C37.118, which defines a method for exchanging synchronized phasor measurement data between power system devices, is represented in addition to the main protocols. This protocol can be considered an alternative to SV within IEC 61850.

When analyzing the elements in the test environments, it was found that the most common elements were S/IED (39x), C/IED (34x), and SCADA (22x). From the perspective of the implementation of the test environment, this representation is quite logical. IEDs or server stations are relatively simple to implement (virtual, simulated, or emulated) and

affordable for physical devices. To ensure valid S/IED communication, a counterpart must be implemented, which can be represented by C/IED, (M/R)TU, SCADA, or HMI stations, which all environments meet. It is also important to highlight that in 19 articles, an Attacker's presence was simulated, which shows the importance of cyber security in these test environments.

The purpose of test environments is one of the critical aspects of analyzing energy research. In the analysis of the test environments, 33 articles were found to emphasize security aspects. This number indicates the growing need to protect energy systems from cyber threats. With the increasing number of cyber attacks on critical infrastructure, it is essential to have a detailed knowledge of potential system vulnerabilities and how to address them. Next, 17 papers focused on data generation and simulation. This figure shows the growing need to protect power systems from cyber threats. Given the increasing number of cyber attacks on critical infrastructure, a detailed understanding of potential system vulnerabilities and how to address them is essential. Although only eight articles focused on education, it is essential to recognize that training and educating energy professionals is critical to future innovation and ensuring security.

Of the 42 articles analyzed, it was found that the article [40] represented the most comprehensive approach to the topic, as it met the most criteria in the table, that is, 14 criteria. This is a physical environment with some emulated parts. According to the article, all the most used protocols are represented. Similarly, all the main elements from the IED station to SCADA are represented from an infrastructure perspective. The article focuses primarily on the security area of industrial and critical infrastructure automated systems. A disadvantage of the environment may be the absence of virtualized or simulated parts interconnected with the physical ones, thus providing more variability in case of new scenarios or use for other purposes. Whether it be education or data generation for other purposes. The second most comprehensive test environment is described in [18], which met the 13 criteria defined in the table. This environment combines virtual, emulated, and physical elements. As far as communication protocols are concerned, the article covers IEC 60870, DNP3 and Modbus TCP. All essential elements are represented in the infrastructure area, including SCADA, HMI, MTU/RTU and IED units.

The type of testbed implementation, whether virtual, emulated or physical, is a crucial criterion for determining its ability to mimic real energy systems and can affect its flexibility, realism and responsiveness to different research scenarios. Furthermore, communication protocols in the energy sector are the building blocks for information transfer, and their proper representation and analysis are essential to adequately address the fundamental challenges associated with communication in energy networks. Communication elements such as servers, clients, IEDs, MTUs, RTUs, SCADA and HMI are critical components of power systems.

Analyzing and integrating them into the test environment is essential for a comprehensive view of power systems, and by incorporating attacker simulation, we can also better understand potential security threats. Determining the purpose of the test environment, whether it is data generation, education, or cybersecurity, allows us to focus the research on specific areas of interest and ensures that the results are relevant and applicable to the target audience. Ultimately, meeting all of the criteria in the table results in high-quality and comprehensive research that effectively addresses current and future energy challenges.

While many existing testbeds address specific criteria effectively, they often fall short in providing a comprehensive solution that integrates all critical aspects simultaneously. This gap underscores the need for a testbed that not only meets but exceeds these requirements by combining a modular architecture, extensive protocol support, and the ability to simulate diverse scenarios.

The comparison in Table 1 reveals that most existing testbeds focus on specific aspects, such as either purely physical components or limited support for standards, which restricts their flexibility and interoperability. In contrast, BUTENET integrates a wide range of standards (e.g., IEC 61850, IEC 60870, ModBus, DNP3) and combines physical, emulated, and virtualized components. This modular architecture enables detailed analysis of cyber threats and the simulation of complex scenarios, including critical events in transmission networks. The addition of innovative tools, such as the digital twin and cyber arena, enhances its utility for both education and research.

III. BRNO UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY ELECTRICAL NETWORK TESTBED

Brno University of Technology Electrical Network Testbed (BUTENET) was designed to overcome the limitations of existing solutions and provide a comprehensive and modular framework in the key areas of realization, protocols, components, and purpose that were defined in Table 1. Our testbed covers the full spectrum of realizations from virtual and simulated systems, to emulated devices, to physical components. This arrangement enables detailed testing in a wide range of scenarios and optimizes the flexibility of the testing process. Our testbed covers the full spectrum of implementations from virtual and simulated systems, to emulated devices, to physical components. This layout enables detailed testing in a wide range of scenarios and optimizes the flexibility of the testing process.

The testbed's modular architecture was designed with scalability in mind. For example, the Raspberry Pi cluster can be expanded by adding additional nodes, or its functionality can be augmented with more powerful single-board computers, such as Nvidia Jetson Nano, for scenarios requiring GPU acceleration. Similarly, the virtual component of the testbed can be scaled by provisioning additional virtual machines on the underlying infrastructure, allowing the system to accommodate larger networks or more complex attack scenarios.

The ability to mix and match physical, emulated, and virtual components has proven essential in adapting the testbed to different research and educational goals. For example, virtual components can simulate large-scale network attacks in a cybersecurity training scenario, while physical devices provide realistic feedback. This flexibility demonstrates the testbed's capability to transition seamlessly between research on energy resilience and practical education for students.

We integrate a wide range of industrial communication protocols such as IEC 61850, and IEC 60870 standards, Modbus, DNP3 or OPC UA, ensuring that our testbed can support and validate different types of data exchange and interoperability between disparate systems and devices. IEC 61850 was selected as the primary protocol for communication in electrical substations because of its advanced features. The standard is continuously being updated with new parts covering current topics such as renewable energy IEC 61850-90-7 or charging point management for electric vehicles IEC 61850-90-8. This is also an increasingly represented standard within the European Union regarding communication in electrical substations. The standard is designed to meet time (GOOSE, SV) and data (MMS) critical standards for current and future development. DNP3 is now a rather outdated standard that can still be used without limitations at present. However, with the ever-increasing automation and digitalization of electrical substations, with ever-increasing demands on the speed of response to anomalous events, more is needed in the future.

IEC 60870 was preferred over DNP3 primarily based on its compatibility with IEC 61850, specifically the IEC 61850-80-1 standard, which describes data forwarding and mapping. The second criterion that favoured IEC 60870 is its geographic applicability. The authors of this article are primarily focused on the European Union's electrification system; standards cover this stage, whether it is the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol for communication between RTU and SCADA or IEC 60870-6 for communication between SCADA. However, a closer look at the DNP3 standard is planned in the future.

The Modbus and OPC UA protocols were chosen as complementary, as they are used in some systems, either as support systems that serve as complementary but have a link to primary systems, for example, in electrical racks. This can be heating or cooling in these stations, controlling HVAC and other systems but affecting the primary system. Modbus is now a relatively obsolete standard, but its use is still extensive due to its simplicity. Even though it is no longer the primary protocol in new equipment today, it is still found in equipment and can be communicated. For example, if the proton is not disabled, an attacker can control the device and access the system through it. OPC UA is a newer and more robust standard, but it is increasingly used in OT systems connected to power systems, as mentioned above.

From an infrastructure perspective, we focus on key elements such as SCADA systems, HMIs, MTUs, RTUs, IEDs

as well as simulating attackers to test security aspects. This approach ensures that our tests realistically reflect potential threats and vulnerabilities. The focus of our testbed is in the areas of education, data generation and cybersecurity. In doing so, it provides a significant contribution to developing new protection strategies and improving the resilience of power systems.

The basis for the implementation of our testbed was the Power System (PS) of the Czech Republic, where transmission system (TS), operated by CEPS a.s., is a critical component of the power system, linking major entities like power plants and regional networks, and playing a vital role in international grid cooperation. This system includes overhead lines totaling 5,848 km across various voltage levels (400 kV, 220 kV, and 110 kV) and features 44 substations with 75 transformers to facilitate energy transformation and distribution. Plans are underway to standardize the network to 400 kV and enhance the telecommunications infrastructure using optical ground wires. CEPS is responsible for the reliable operation and development of this complex network, which includes transmission lines, substations, and control systems. The dispatch control system, equipped to European standards, ensures operational management and real-time support. The system is interconnected with neighboring countries' grids, enhancing regional cooperation. The dispatch system aids in standard operations and crisis situations, helping manage voltage and power flows and enabling remote control of substations. CEPS also develops plans to prevent and mitigate system failures and to restore the grid after major disturbances, ensuring compliance with safety standards, including the (N-1) criterion for operational reliability. In summary, the TS is integral to the Czech energy infrastructure, ensuring stability, security, and integration with European grids.

BUTENET is divided into main parts, physical and virtual. The representation of the entire testbed is shown in Figure 1. The left part shows the physical parts of the testbed, where the core is an RPi cluster composed of 50 Raspberry Pi 3B+ (RPi) with the Raspbian operating system. The design of the RPi cluster took place early in the project in 2020, where different variants of single board computers were selected with respect to availability, reliability, performance, support and cost. Based on these criteria, the Raspberry Pi single board computers were found to be unsuitable. Due to the Raspbian operating system that was developed specifically for these units and their support due to their similarity to the Debian OS, they appeared to be the most suitable candidates. Performance and price matched competing devices in the same class. The last criterion was reliability, where since the fourth version (release date June 2019) was only on the market for a short time, the older but proven and more than sufficient third version in the B+ model was chosen.

While Raspberry Pi 3B+ provides an excellent balance of cost and performance, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations compared to more advanced hardware. Specifically:

- *Performance Constraints in Large-Scale Simulations* - Raspberry Pi 3B+ features a quad-core ARM Cortex-A53 CPU and 1 GB of RAM, which may need to be improved for large-scale grid simulations requiring high-speed parallel data processing or the emulation of complex transient phenomena. More advanced devices, such as Raspberry Pi 4 with up to 8 GB of RAM, offer greater computational capabilities suitable for such scenarios.
- *Network Throughput for Cybersecurity Applications* - Although Raspberry Pi 3B+ is equipped with a Gigabit Ethernet port, its throughput is limited by the USB 2.0 bus that connects the Ethernet module, reducing practical speeds to around 200–300 Mbps. This limitation may pose challenges for high-speed network traffic scenarios, such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) simulations. In contrast, Raspberry Pi 4 has a true Gigabit Ethernet interface with a dedicated controller, enabling significantly higher and more consistent throughput.
- *High-Performance Computational Tasks* - Applications involving machine learning, predictive diagnostics, or detailed transient stability analysis may exceed Raspberry Pi 3B+'s capabilities. With its GPU-accelerated processing, alternatives like Nvidia Jetson Nano are better suited for such tasks, providing enhanced performance for computationally intensive operations.

Despite these limitations, Raspberry Pi 3B+ remains highly suitable for emulating typical devices in energy systems. Most RTUs, IEDs, and HMIs used in the energy sector are built on low-performance hardware with similar or lower capabilities. These devices are optimized for specific tasks, such as data collection, signal processing, and communication, and Raspberry Pi 3B+ matches or exceeds their performance. Its compatibility with industrial protocols, including IEC 61850, DNP3, and Modbus, ensures it can realistically emulate these systems within the testbed.

Moreover, the modular architecture of the BUTENET testbed allows for straightforward upgrades or replacements if more demanding applications arise. For example:

- Raspberry Pi 4 Model B, with its upgraded CPU, GPU, and up to 8 GB of RAM, could seamlessly replace Raspberry Pi 3B+ without major software changes due to the compatibility of the Raspbian (now Raspberry Pi OS) platform.
- Alternatives such as Nvidia Jetson Nano or BeagleBone Black could be integrated to address specific high-performance requirements, such as machine learning or advanced cybersecurity simulations.

To enhance the clarity of Figure 1, a detailed legend is provided below, explaining the main components and their functions. The figure illustrates three primary categories: physical, virtual, and emulated components, all

FIGURE 1. Brno University of Technology Electrical Network testbed.

interconnected through a network infrastructure. These categories are further detailed as follows:

- *Physical Components* - Signal Emulator: A device simulating physical electrical signals (e.g., currents, voltages); Real Devices: Actual industrial devices (e.g., RTU, IED, Merging Unit) that enhance the fidelity of simulations.
- *Virtual Components* - SCADA: A system for monitoring and controlling electrical substations, a key part of the physical infrastructure.; HMI (Human Machine Interface): A local interface enabling operators to monitor and control devices.; Cyber Arena: A virtual environment for simulating cyberattacks and testing defensive mechanisms.; Digital Twin: A digital model of a city connected to the transmission and distribution network, allowing for complex scenario simulations.
- *Emulated Components* - RPi Cluster: A group of 50 Raspberry Pi devices simulating various parts of electrical substations, such as MTU or RTU.
- *Network Infrastructure* - Ensures the interconnection of all physical, virtual, and emulated components of the testbed using network elements.
- *Management Station* - The central control unit for managing the testbed, enabling configuration, monitoring, and control of all components.

Of these, 47 RPi represent the main terminal unit (MTU) of a substation or power plant that communicates with the SCADA system within the Czech Republic transmission system (see Figure 2). Each of these RPis is connected to a graphical display that shows the critical values for the unit. The remaining three RPi emulate one substation according to the IEC 61850 standard (see Chapter III-B for more details).

Other testbed parts are Real devices, Signal emulator, Management station and Network Infrastructure. Currently, we have real devices - Merging unit (MU), Intelligent Electronic Device (IED) and Remote Terminal Unit (RTU) from ABB and Siemens. The Signal emulator is a device we developed that allows simulating electrical inputs (current, voltage, binary states) to the above-mentioned real devices Merging unit and Protection Relay. The management station manages the whole testbed and allows, e.g., to install, update or renew of all devices. The last part is the Network infrastructure, which connects all components through network elements.

The second part of the testbed is Virtual, where the core is a cluster, a collection of servers with virtualization tools.

FIGURE 2. Visual part of Czech Republic transmission system with RPi cluster.

Here the openMUC software is virtualized, representing the SCADA system for all the devices in the testbed. In addition, the HMI unit simulator is built on the same software. Furthermore, Virtual devices are simulated in the Virtual cluster, e.g., the equivalent of the emulated devices on the RPi. Therefore, the system can achieve a more significant number of devices connected to only one physical interface.

The testbed is part of a more extensive system designed for research and educational purposes. In this system, two tools, Digital Twin [58], [59] and Cyber Arena [60], [61], are associated with the described testbed. Digital Twin is a digital system modelling tool based on the NS-3.² In our case, it is a city model where energy and data infrastructures are modelled. The testbed within the model simulates the electrical transmission and distribution network connected to the modelled city. Cyber Arena is an educational and training tool built on the OpenStack virtualization tool. testbed is part of training and educational scenarios focused on the electric transmission and distribution network.

Besides the advantages, various problems arose during the development process, where the most important ones are listed below. The combination of devices from different manufacturers (e.g., ABB and Siemens) revealed differences in protocol implementation. Resolving these differences required custom configurations to standardize communication. Also, communication between IEC 61850 and IEC 60870-5-104 protocols was a challenge in the early days, where the IEC 61850-80-1 standard had to be implemented based on documentation, as no open-source variant was available. The management of all devices, e.g., the RPi cluster, initially seemed like a simple task. However, the opposite became true. Running a large number of applications at the same time to easily establish communication so that all stations started correctly required thorough verification. Similarly, managing the power supply to all the units in the RPi cluster to avoid voltage fluctuations when they were switched on was very complicated.

²<https://www.nsnam.org>

FIGURE 3. Management application interface.

A. TESTBED MANAGEMENT

A Web application has been developed for efficient testbed management. It allows monitoring and control of physical components (RPI cluster, Signal emulator) and real devices (IEDs, TRUs) of the created testbed. This Web application uses the Django³ framework. Django stands out as an ideal choice for testbed and device management due to its robust features and design principles. At the core of Django's effectiveness is its *Model-view-controller* architecture, a framework that cleanly separates the application into three distinct components—data model, user interface, and control logic. This architectural approach ensures that modifications to one component have minimal impact on the others, enhancing the application's scalability and maintainability. The decision to employ Django was motivated by its platform-agnostic nature, enabling seamless cross-platform control without being tied to specific hardware dependencies. This not only ensures flexibility in managing the testbed, but also positions the application for future scalability and adaptability.

The application is composed of Web pages. The signpost is the *Homepage*, to which the user is redirected after logging in on the *Login page*. The *Live Map* page (see Figure 3) serves as a simple interface for the user to monitor events in the testbed in a simplified manner. The page displays each station's simulated layout and states (Active, Connected, Disconnected) in real-time. It also informs the user about the appropriate states of the running-state scenarios. The second key page *Server list* contains a complete list of stations that includes all the functions to configure and edit traffic. This page is therefore intended for advanced testbed setup.

B. ELECTRICAL SUBSTATION

The substation is an important part of the transmission and distribution network, which ensures the interconnection of the transmission lines and distribution lines, as well as the transformation between different voltage levels, or the compensation of reactive power, or in some cases the conversion of alternating current to other frequencies

³<https://www.djangoproject.com/>

FIGURE 4. Substation structure.

or direct current. According to the IEC 61850 standard, an electrical station is divided into three levels: Process, Bay, and Station. The structure is shown in Figure 4. In the left part in the column Level devices, the block diagram for each level and their connection to the communication Process bus or Station bus is shown. The Process level is the lowest level of the station where the power devices are contacted. At this level, the most common devices are merging units, which convert analog signals from the voltage and current instrument transformers and merge them into a standardized digital output format. The Sampled values (SV) protocol transmits digital data to higher levels. The merging units also have the GOOSE protocol for critical messages between devices. The merging unit can also be used to control switching devices such as a circuit breaker (CB), disconnector (DC), or earthing switch (ES). The control is carried out via binary outputs. Similarly, the merging unit can sense the switching elements' states using binary inputs. According to the IEC 61850 standard, the next level is the Bay level, where IEDs are located. The Protection Unit (PU) and the Power Quality Meter (PQ) primarily fall under this designation. In the case of larger electrical stations, the Remote Terminal Unit (RTU) for remote control may also be located here. The highest level of the electrical station is the Station level, where data collection, visualization, and transmission of the monitored electrical system status takes place. The prominent representatives of this level are the Master Terminal Unit for remote control of the substation, the Human Machine Interface for local control of devices, the Power Quality Analyzer for comprehensive evaluation of archived PQ measurement data and fault records, and the Gateway as the interface between the LAN and the WAN.

The implementation of the electrical substation is performed in two variants, physical and emulated (see Figure 4). The physical one consists of devices from Siemens and ABB, one of the leading suppliers of intelligent electrical substations in the Czech Republic. The emulated one is built on Raspberry Pi 3B+ single board computers (RPi), where one RPi implements each substation level.

1) IMPLEMENTED PROCESS LEVEL

The physical part of the Process level is implemented using ABB SMU615, Siemens SIPROTEC 6MU85 and Signal

FIGURE 5. Signal simulator diagram.

Simulator. ABB and Siemens devices are MUs that primarily communicate using protocols from the IEC 61850 standard. The management protocol is MMS, which allows remote configuration and values readings. The SV protocol publisher handles the transmission of the sampled digital voltage and current data from the instrument transformers. In addition, the GOOSE publisher sends time-critical messages with information such as switching element states, protection operation, or other similar signals.

The analog voltage and current values sensed in a real environment with the instrument transformers are simulated by the Signal Simulator, which transfers them in a defined format to the MU. In addition, Signal Simulator simulates binary state values representing CB, DC and ES devices.

Signal Simulator is based on the Arduino nano platform (see Figure 5), which receives control commands via USB or ethernet port from the Management station. The simulator's output is a 3-phase sinusoidal voltage, a 3-phase current and binary values simulating states, e.g., CB, DC or ES, to be connected to MU or IED. In real-world applications, Merging Units and Protection Relays are connected to voltage and current transformers that scale down high voltage levels (e.g., 110 kV) to manageable levels (e.g., 100 V) suitable for electronic processing. Similarly, current transformers scale down to high current levels for safe operating ranges. The Signal Simulator replicates these scaled-down signals, allowing the emulation of realistic operational conditions. The simulator achieves this using an Arduino Nano coupled with a transformer, phase-shifting circuitry, and additional components. These elements generate three-phase sinusoidal voltage and current signals, each phase precisely offset by 120 degrees. The voltage and current levels can be controlled and maintained at predefined low voltages, ensuring compatibility with the Merging Units and Protection Relays without requiring high-power components. The accuracy of the signal simulator is on the order of tens of millivolts, which is sufficient for the intended applications. Absolute accuracy is not a top priority, as deviations of a few tens of volts or even hundreds of volts have negligible impact in the context of a 110 kV system since units of kV are monitored at such high voltages. If we convert this to the 100 V we have shown, 1 kV corresponds to approximately 0.9 V, which is more than sufficient for the simulator's accuracy.

To simulate a 3-phase voltage or current, an Arduino 3-phase sinusoidal signal is generated using PWM modulation (see Figure 6). This signal goes to a reconstruction filter implemented by a low-pass filter that smooths the sinusoidal signal. Subsequently, the DC signal component is filtered out using a smoothing capacitor. The last part is the

FIGURE 6. Signal Simulator - Voltage and Current diagram.

amplifier element of an operational amplifier in an inverter connection. The Resistive divider shown in Figure 6 controls the magnitude of the output voltage. Finally, the output current magnitude is adjusted using a digital potentiometer controlled by Arduino.

The emulated part of the Process level is implemented by the RPi unit. The implementation is done in C++ programming language with *libiec61850*⁴ library from MZ automation, which is the core for simulating the communication of MMS, GOOSE and SV protocols. MMS is a client-server control protocol for remote device control or data acquisition. The GOOSE protocol was developed to transmit critical device states in real-time. The primary purpose is to inform other devices of the status of critical elements (e.g., CB, DC, or ES) and to command other devices (e.g., switch CB state) in the shortest possible time (in some cases, within 3 ms). The last SV protocol transmits sampled voltages and currents in a real-time to the parent devices.

Four devices are implemented in the emulated version of the Process level - MU, CB, DC, and ES. The merging unit emulates data from the current and voltage transformers that would be connected to the monitored power line in a real scenario and sends them to the parent units using the SV protocol. The data are generated using a pseudo-random number generator continuously, simulating a sinusoidal signal and in a defined range (e.g., 400kV/220kV for transmission system or 110kV/22kV for distribution system) according to the specified voltage level for the standard operation scenario. In case of the other scenarios, including voltage instability, overcurrent, short circuit (either fatal or recoverable), the requisite adjustments are implemented to address the specific conditions that trigger the scenario.

CB, DC and ES are very similar devices in implementation. In a real environment, they are connected to an MU or PU unit and are controlled by binary commands. In the standard state, these devices are in an open state or close state, depending on the wiring of the monitored system, and send periodic messages to the parent devices. In the event of a physical or remote change of the switching device state, a nonperiodic message is generated to indicate a change in device status. Thus, the operator is informed that the requested state change has actually been performed. Within the emulated station, n devices of type CB, DC or ES with their identifier can be started and assigned a role within the configuration file to the MU or IED, as outlined in Figure 4.

2) IMPLEMENTED BAY LEVEL

The Bay level is an intermediate level between Process and Station that primarily contains Intelligent Electronic Devices

(IEDs) such as protective relays, measuring units, and control units that perform the first level of data processing from sensors and other devices at the process level. Here, IEDs perform protection, measurement, control, and more functions.

In our solution, the Physical part includes ABB RE(x)615 and Siemens Siprotec 7SJ85 devices, which serve as protective devices in substations. Due to different protocol configurations, the ABB device has three variants: ABB REF615, REC615, and RER615. The basic communication protocol for these devices is IEC 61850. However, ABB offers the possibility of other standards, such as Modbus TCP, IEC 60870 (protocols 101, 103 and 104), and DNP3, represented in our devices. This allows us to react variably to possible scenarios where these protocols need to be used. The Siemens Siprotec 7SJ85 is a very similar device to the ABB RE(x)615. The basic communication protocol is IEC 61850, which can be extended with the protocols mentioned for the ABB RE(x)615, depending on the configuration. In our case, IEC 60870-5-104 and Modbus TCP are represented. The duplication of the two manufacturers was chosen based on safety requirements to ensure continuous protection in the event that one of the devices fails. In real operation, two devices from different manufacturers are constantly in use to ensure higher security if there is, for example, a problem on a specific type of device, either in its HW or SW part. The last device in this section is the Siemens SICAM P850, a multifunctional device for acquiring, visualizing, evaluating and transmitting measured electrical quantities such as AC, AC voltage, frequency, power, harmonics, etc.

Within the Emulated part of the Bay level, as in the case of the Process level, a Raspberry Pi 3B+ unit is used, where libraries simulating the communication and states commonly found at this level are implemented. Regarding communication, these are the MMS control protocol and Publisher/Subscriber for the SV and GOOSE protocols. The RPI is configured to emulate the ABB and Siemens devices mentioned above as faithfully as possible. The advantage over real devices is the ability to simulate a higher number of devices and a simple and less expensive option if additional devices are needed.

3) IMPLEMENTED STATION LEVEL

At the Station Level, some systems have an overview of the entire electrical station. This includes various computer systems such as MTU or RTU, HMI, databases, and other servers. This level processes data from the Bay Level IEDs and often performs more complex analysis and decision making.

The Physical part of our solution includes ABB COM600 and Siemens SICAM A8000. ABB COM600 is a universal unit for automation and data management in substations. The unit receives data from the ABB RE(x)615 protection units, processes, evaluates, and communicates with the master monitoring centre. The Siemens SICAM A8000 is a very similar unit to the ABB COM600. The data generated from

⁴<https://github.com/mz-automation/libiec61850>

the SIEMENS Sipotec 7SJ85 and SICAM 850 are processed, evaluated in the unit, and networked to the parent monitoring centre.

In the Emulated part of our solution, as in the previous one, a Raspberry Pi 3B+ unit is used, which allows simulating/emulating communication for the IEC 61850 and IEC 60870 standards in several variants. The first variant is a terminal client station for the IEC 61850 standard. In this case, the MMS protocol can issue terminal commands to selected devices. Receiving and processing data from the SV and GOOSE protocols is also possible. This variant is not suitable for real operations as it does not directly simulate any device. However, in the case of device testing or use as a source unit to simulate an attacker, it is more suitable than the variants described in the following. The second variant is a local HMI built on the OpenMUC platform. It is a station with a graphical interface that can be configured according to the requirements of the scenario. The MMS protocol is primarily used within the substation, to which Process and Bay level devices are connected. In addition to the MMS protocol, IEC 60870-5-104 or Modbus TCP can be used if necessary. The graphical interface and the device communication configuration are configured through a Web interface or XML configuration file to provide variability when changing scenarios. The third option is a translator of the IEC 61850 standard to IEC 60870-5-104 defined within IEC 61850-80-1, which is described below. This station allows control and data collection from the monitoring center, which primarily communicates using the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol, to the end devices within the electrical substation, where communication is via the MMS protocol.

4) IEC 61850 CLIENT

The IEC 61850-80-1 standard was implemented in the field station because of its wide use and benefits for testing. Its common use in the industry provides us with a robust framework for performing tests with high reliability and accuracy. The implementation of this standard allows compatibility and interoperability with other equipment and systems in the power sector. IEC 61850-80-1 extends the original IEC 61850 standard and provides guidance for the exchange of information from the CDC⁵ data model to IEC 60870-5-101/104. With this standard, we have achieved efficient two-way communication that allows us to remotely monitor and control the substation equipment through a Web interface. The flow of message conversion between the MMS protocol (from IEC 61850) and IEC 60870-5-104 is shown in Figure 7.

This diagram details the exchange of individual messages at the application level between devices in our infrastructure. The simplified structure includes *IEC 61850 Server*, which can be represented by a real device and a virtual one. Thus, it can be an ABB REF615, P850, or a virtual RTU device. The

FIGURE 7. Message conversion diagram between MMS and IEC 60870-5-104 protocols.

other elements are *IEC 61850 Client* and *IEC 60870-5-104 Server*, which form the core of the testbed station and provide message transfer between the protocols mentioned above according to the IEC 61850-80-1 standard. These elements are implemented on individual RPi within the RPi cluster. Again, the solution also allows for operation on a virtual device, thus eliminating the need for a specific device for actual functionality. The last element is the *IEC 60870-5-104 Client*. This is represented within our infrastructure by the control center (i.e., the OpenMUC server).

Two sending sequences are shown within the diagram: (1) the periodic message and (2) the command message. Periodic messages are initialized from the *IEC 61850 Client* station and send a periodic request to *IEC 61850 Server*. The response is passed to *IEC 60870-5-104 Server*, which creates a new message from the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol within the mapping table. The periodic message is then sent to *IEC 60870-5-104 Client*, which processes the value and stores it in the value database if necessary. a similar procedure is used for command communication, except that the initiator of communication in this case is *IEC 60870-5-104 Client*.

The first sequence shows the sequence of sending periodic messages for the value *MMXU\$AvAphs* on the *IEC 61850 Server* station. This represents the arithmetic average of the current magnitude of the 3 phases. It is remapped to the *M_ME_TF_1* data type as part of the interprotocol conversion, which represents the measured value with a short floating point, and also adds the timestamp “CP56Time2a”. The second sequence shows the sequence when the command is sent from the control center. This message has the data type *C_DC_NA_1*, which represents double command without time tag. This can represent, for example, a change of switch position (*CSWISPos*). This request is remapped to the MMS request format and sent to *IEC 61850 Server*. After the requested command is executed, *IEC 61850 Server* sends an MMS response which is remapped to the message type *M_DP_NA_1*. This format is used for the response to the message type *C_DC_NA_1* which carries the new value set by the command.

⁵This is a data model used in various communication standards such as IEC 61850

5) IEC 60870-5-101/104 SERVER

The structure of the Czech Republic transmission and distribution system is defined in depth by a set of standards, the key document is Grid Code.⁶ This standard sets out the technical, design, and operational requirements for the connection and use of the transmission system to ensure its functionality even in unusual situations. However, it is important to note that similar standards exist in other countries, particularly within Europe. Despite slight variations in national regulations, this standardization has an impact on the quality of energy services provided. In our case, we have carefully respected these standards in the design of the testbed and derived from them the critical conditions and situations that we try to prevent.

Within the testbed, there are five basic scenarios that allow simulating the most common situations in TS and DS: (1) Standard operation, (2) Voltage instability (includes Undervoltage and Overvoltage), (3) Overcurrent, (4) Short circuit (includes fatal and recoverable) and (5) standard manipulations “Service”. The first four scenarios have been designed to represent the most common conditions in which real TS stations (or the whole system) may be in. In addition, we have also created a fifth scenario covering standard equipment handling to cover basic equipment maintenance, which is an integral part of the operation. All scenarios were implemented directly in the emulated station with the possibility of remote interaction using the management server or locally using configuration files.

The IEC 60870-5-104 protocol was chosen for data communication within a testbed. The protocol is an International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) standard and is used worldwide for data transmission in power networks. The protocol is used to transfer data between control centers, bus devices, and metering and control equipment in electricity networks. It is an application protocol that uses protocols from the TCP/IP model for transmission within the network. At the transport layer, the TCP state protocol is used to ensure the reliability of the transmitted data.

To simulate and test the secure communication, in addition to the classic non-secure communication of the IEC 60870-5-101/104 protocol, a TLS protocol extension was implemented in the testbed. This meets the requirements of the IEC 62351 standard for ensuring the security of transmitted data. The electrical station and control center are designed to make it easy to switch between these versions.

To simulate a power station or a power plant in the transmission or distribution system communicating with SCADA, a program was implemented that simulates the data communication of the IEC 60870-5-101/104 protocol. For the program code, the library *lib60870-2.3.0*⁷ was chosen, which contains all the basic functions for working with the communication protocol, including functions to establish TCP and TLS connections.

⁶<https://www.ceps.cz/cs/kodex-ps>

⁷<https://www.mz-automation.de/>

TABLE 2. Simulated data by polygon electric station.

NoO	IOA range	Meaning of data
12	1000–1011	The data represent input values of the physical quantities voltage (U), current (I), active (P) and reactive (Q) power for all 3 measured phases.
12	2000–2011	The data represent output values of the physical quantities voltage (U), current (I), active (P) and reactive (Q) power for all 3 measured phases.
5	3000–3002	The data represent transformer temperature (TT), ambient temperature (AT), frequency (f).
5	4000–4003	The data represent the states of the protective elements, CB, ES, and DS.
5	5000–5013	The data represent the states of defined events (e.g. CB tripping or alarm triggering). In addition, they convey alarm information conditions: system overvoltage/undervoltage, overcurrent, short circuit.

Each station is configured to receive commands from the adjacent station and send appropriate responses. It also acts as a data emulator, sending periodic (or spontaneous) data to the adjacent station for further processing. In the case of a quiescent state, when these stations are not subject to any undesirable influences, they emulate data according to Table 2.

To display the most important data to the user, all emulated stations have a connected I2C OLED information display (see Figure 2). Information display cannot effectively display a large amount of data. For this reason, only the most important data for the operation of the station have been prioritized. These are the primary and secondary voltage and temperature values of the transformer. In addition to the data already mentioned, there is service information about the IP address of the device, its current transformer display, the network status (NET), the status of the generation of the values corresponding to the quiescent state (PWR) and the current time at the bottom of the display.

When the station emulation starts, periodic messages (PM) are sent. Subsequently, the system is checked to see if there are any problems in the network. If no problem occurs, periodic data are sent again. Otherwise, non-periodic messages (NPM) are sent in addition to the periodic messages. NPMs are sent only when a scenario or an error occurs in the system.

A configuration file provides the implementation of critical states. The station’s behavior changes if an error condition is written to this file. All error conditions and brief descriptions are shown in Table 3.

We will now focus on the key aspects of the operational scenarios developed. As part of the definition of these scenarios, we have created a set of internal actions by analyzing a real device (ABB REF615) and applying them to the generated messages sent to the control center (in our case, the OpenMUC server). It is important to emphasize that the main goal was not the realistic generation of physical

TABLE 3. Defined field station states.

State Name	Description
0 Voltage instability	NPM alarm and warning - undervoltage, overvoltage and alarm activation
1 Standard operation	Normal program running, only PM
2 Overcurrent	NPM about OC, TRP, CB
3 Short circuit (fatal/reinit)	NPM about OC, TRIP, CB, RECLOSE
4 Standard manipulations	PM about status, NPM about status change, NPM about commands

quantities (U, I, P, f) but the actual behavioral behavior of the individual transformers as a whole. The generated values of the physical variables are continuously generated according to the daily load diagram created and represent the data transmitted to the control center at set intervals. The load has been carefully created based on publicly available data provided by CEPS,⁸ which allows us to simulate realistic operating conditions.

In the following description, for the sake of clarity and simplicity, we will stick to the description of one transformer unit within one station, where there can be up to four such units in one station. By default, each station runs a standard operation scenario in which no unexpected or undesired events are triggered.

1) Standard operation: The standard operation simulates the behavior of the transformer, where the measured physical quantities are simulated and their respective communication to the control center. In standard operation, the station simulates input and output voltage data (U_a, U_b, U_c) in the range 380–420 kV for the 400 kV voltage level, 209–231 kV for the 220 kV level and 99–121 kV for the 110 kV level. It also simulates the magnitude of the input and output currents (I_a, I_b, I_c), which range from tens of A to units of kA depending on the time of day and the load curve mentioned above. Furthermore, the type of the station itself plays a role, whether it simulates the operation of the boundary transformer of the power plant or other substations of the transmission system. To create a realistic simulation, the station also calculates the active (P) and reactive (Q) power. These quantities give us detailed information about the power flow in the system. The dynamic change of phase shift (φ) during the simulation allows to simulate different operating conditions and thus to achieve the truest possible picture of the real situation. Furthermore, functions have been implemented to generate frequency values in the range 49.5–50.5 Hz, for a nominal frequency of 50 Hz. The transformer temperature was modeled in the range of 100–140 °C, while the ambient temperature was set in the range of 15–25 °C, which represents normal ambient conditions.

As far as communication with control center is concerned, only PM messages are sent here. The interval of sending these messages is set to 10 seconds and contains messages

⁸<https://www.ceps.cz/cs/data>

FIGURE 8. (a) Voltage progression of standard operation scenario, undervoltage and overvoltage; (b) Current progression of standard operation scenario, overcurrent, outage with and without restoration.

containing information about the measured (in this case simulated) quantities. These messages are in the range of IOA 1000 to 4004 according to Table 2. In addition to the measured values, the states of the individual protection elements CB, DC, and ES are also sent.

Within this standard operation scenario, there is the possibility to invoke defined subscenarios, and their simplified time courses are illustrated in Figure 8, where there are two graphs - (a) voltage and (b) current. The value of voltage and current on the Y-axis is represented in the graph by a power unit (pu), which represents a normalized coefficient relative to the nominal value, allowing their value to be expressed as a ratio to their nominal value. The X-axis shows the time progression in seconds, which shows the change within the subscenario compared to the standard state, it is not a display of the total time of the subscenario.

Part (a) presents the voltage characteristics for standard operation (green), undervoltage (blue), and overvoltage (red). Also shown are the defined thresholds for sending information on possible overvoltage/undervoltage (light blue) and the thresholds for sending warning messages in case of significant overvoltage/undervoltage (orange). Part (b) provides current time histories for standard operation scenario (green), overcurrent (red), restoration outage (blue), and restoration outage (purple).

2) Undervoltage/Overvoltage: The voltage instability scenario represents a scenario in which the transformed voltage deviates from its nominal value. In this case, only two conditions can occur: (1) undervoltage – reduced voltage level and (2) overvoltage – increased voltage level. Both of these states can escalate to 2 levels: (1) informational (non-critical deviation) and (2) warning (critical deviation from the nominal voltage). In this case, the NPMs are sent to the control center in addition to the PMs. Within the NPMs, alarm messages are sent on the occurrence of a non-critical event, or messages regarding a critical

condition – alarm triggering and a specific event (critical undervoltage/overvoltage).

3) Overcurrent: Electricity storage is a resource-intensive and time-consuming operation. Electricity-generating plants cannot produce random amounts of energy. The electrical system must be maintained in a so-called balanced state, which occurs when the amount of energy produced matches the amount of energy consumed. When this balance is disturbed, the system experiences an overvoltage (when overproduction occurs) or an undervoltage (when overconsumption occurs). If the control center does not adequately compensate for these deviations, the system or part of it may fail.

The Overcurrent scenario simulates an overcurrent situation in the electrical system, resulting in a safety shutdown of the station. The scenario simulates a gradual increase in current starting at time $t = 5\text{ s}$ (see Figure 8 (b)). At time $t = 12\text{ s}$ the protective elements react and a safety trip occurs. During the subsequent response of the protective elements, the NPM of the state of the protective elements (DC and CB) and information about the change of the state of these elements is sent. Messages are also sent about alarm triggering and critical overcurrent events. After the overcurrent problem is resolved and the protective elements are returned to their original state, the control center is informed by new NPMs and is switched to the standard operation scenario.

4) Short circuit: A short circuit in an electrical system occurs when there is an undesired connection of electrical conductors with different potentials, resulting in a sudden and uncontrolled overflow of electric current. These situations can arise for a variety of reasons, including physical damage to the insulation, defective equipment, or human error in the handling of the equipment. Simulating a short circuit is important because it allows testing of the electrical system's response to this critical event. Identifying and understanding system behavior during a short circuit is the key to designing safety measures, safeguards, and strategies to minimize the risk of damage to equipment and to ensure fast and reliable shutdown in the event of a major problem. Simulating a short circuit thus allows safety procedures to be refined and optimized while minimizing potential damage to the electrical distribution system.

The Short Circuit scenario is designed to run in two variants, namely (1) with subsequent restoration of service or (2) without subsequent restoration of service. This scenario can be divided into two main phases: (1) simulated outage and (2) subsequent response from the station. The whole situation is displayed in Figure 8. In the first phase, a simulated outage is triggered at time $t = 5.5\text{ s}$. It occurs with a step increase in current that causes an almost instantaneous reaction of the protective elements. During this event, NPMs are sent regarding the status of the short-circuit protection, short-circuit protection switching events, and short-circuit alarms, as well as information about the status

and changes of DC and CB. For the second phase, station response, there are two possible options. The first is the response with subsequent restoration of the operation (shown in blue in the figure). Here, the station will successfully attempt to resume operation. In this action, NPMs are sent regarding the CB change and change events. Subsequently, the standard traffic scenario is executed again. The second option represents the station response without subsequent resumption of operation (marked purple in the figure). In the failed attempt to resume operation at time $t = 6\text{ s}$, NPMs are sequentially sent, similar to the first phase, that is, short circuit protection status, short circuit protection switching events, short circuit alarms, and information on DC, CB status, and changes.

5) Standard manipulations “Service”: Substation servicing is a common and essential part of the operation of electrical substations, ensuring optimal maintenance and trouble-free operation of power systems. The “Service” scenario represents a simulation of the necessary repairs and maintenance of a power substation. This scenario has three variants and takes into account the different safety elements of the station (CB, DC, and ES). The scenario is triggered by sending a command to uncouple (or couple) the element. This action results in the station responding by sending an NPM regarding the change of state of the element. The element is then taken to a logical intermediate position where it waits for the change to be made. The control center is subsequently informed of the uncoupling (or coupling) of the element by another NPM. This process is similar to all the elements mentioned above.

C. SCADA/HMI

To ensure complete monitoring and control of our energy and industrial infrastructure, we have created an integrated monitoring and control center that meets the standards of industrial and energy applications. This center represents our main SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) platform, which effectively serves to centralize the collection, processing, and visualization of data from the entire testbed.

Within this SCADA platform, we use OpenMUC, an open and modular system that allows us to easily monitor and control equipment in industrial and energy networks. The advantages of using OpenMUC lie in its open-source code, modularity, and the ability to be easily adapted to specific needs. The platform offers users the ability to monitor and control equipment in real-time, collect data, and generate useful information for efficient management of energy and industrial systems. It receives and processes data from all devices in the testbed while enabling remote control and monitoring. OpenMUC provides us with the ability to efficiently turn on and modify equipment in a testbed and provide users with clear information about equipment operation. An important feature of this platform is the implementation of a range of industrial and energy protocols, including Modbus, IEC 61850, IEC 60870, OPC UA, DNP3, and their secure variants. This allows us to flexibly and

FIGURE 9. OpenMUC monitoring and control interface for ALB substation.

securely integrate various devices and systems into our infrastructure.

Figure 9 shows a sample of the user interface created for the testbed station. We use this interface to clearly display important information and to control system elements. Our HMI is designed to provide a comprehensive connection to real infrastructure elements using implemented protocols, allowing users to interact with the testbed environment and monitor its status and performance in real-time. This integration offers users advanced visualization and control capabilities, contributing to the efficient management and monitoring of our energy and industrial infrastructure.

IV. TESTBED TESTING

The aim of the following chapter is to determine whether the individual components of the device or the whole testbed are working correctly and whether they meet the quality and reliability requirements. During our tests, we focused mainly on testing the HW components associated with network operation. Testing was carried out through manual procedures, supplemented by the use of specialized tools such as Wireshark and Iperf. The appropriate tools for testing hardware components play a key role in ensuring quality and reliability, as they allow for identification of potential bottlenecks in the system. This identification then enables the implementation of measures to improve performance and optimize overall system functionality. Wireshark was used to analyze network packets, providing a detailed view of the communication between devices. Iperf was subsequently used to measure throughput and data rate, which allowed quantification of system performance and identification of potential areas for optimization.

These tools provided a comprehensive assessment of the testbed’s performance, validating its ability to emulate real-world energy systems effectively. The conducted tests demonstrated the modularity, reliability, and scalability of the testbed design, confirming its suitability for diverse scenarios in smart grid research and education.

TABLE 4. Comparison of data load and delay due to proceedings.

Data	IEC 60870-5-104		TLS 1.1	
	Packet size [B]	Delay [ms]	Packet size [B]	Delay [ms]
Control	493	110	1,948	810
Application	1,225	1.28	1,164	1.48

A. IEC 60870-5-104 COMMUNICATION

In the following section, we focus on the measurement and analysis of the specific protocol properties of the testbed. The IEC 60870-5-104 protocol communication recorded by Wireshark will be discussed. The sizes of each message will be shown, including a comparison of the secure and insecure versions.

Even though the testbed implemented 2 versions of communication (secure and non-secure), the communication method is almost identical. The only difference is in the case of the secure version of the TLS handshake implementation, where certificates are exchanged and connection parameters are established. Once the connection is established, the data transfer can be started.

From the point of view of the network data load, an analysis of secure and non-secure communication of the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol was carried out. The comparison is shown in Table 4. One of the key parameters is the data load. This was divided into 2 parts: (1) control data and (2) application data. The control data represent the protocol messages that are customary to establish or maintain a connection and are non-periodic in nature. In contrast, application data represent messages that carry useful information such as the values of the monitored variables. Here, the periodic character predominates, but an exception can be found in non-periodic messages at certain states that are not included in this analysis. The second parameter observed was the delay incurred due to message processing. This is the delay between the occurrence of the event and the receipt of the message by the monitoring centre. As such, the delay was derived as the difference between the occurrence of the emulated station’s message (the event timestamp) and the entry into the monitoring center’s log system.

B. LOAD TESTING

As part of the tests, a series of tests were carried out focusing on the maximum throughput between the different elements of the testbed. Specifically, the control center (OpenMUC), the management application (Management), and the testbed stations (Station). Data throughput was tested using *iperf*, a network throughput measurement tool. It is a simple network performance testing tool that does not significantly burden the device under test.

The results of these measurements provide useful information on the efficiency of communication within our infrastructure. a set of measurements was taken as part of the tests. Again, each set contained three ten-minute tests that were performed and throughput was measured using both TCP and UDP. The results of the tests are shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5. Throughput between polygon elements.

Connection type	OpenMUC Station	Management Station	Station Station
Transferred payload [GB]	18.7 – 18.8	16.3 – 16.8	18.5 – 18.7
Bandwidth [Mbps]	269	233 – 241	264 – 268
Transferred data-grams [-]	$13.7 \cdot 10^6$	$11.8 - 12.2 \cdot 10^6$	$13.4 - 13.6 \cdot 10^6$
UDP			
Lost datagrams [-]	0 – 4	51 – 339	41 – 127
Lostrate [%]	0 – 0.0003	0.004 – 0.028	0.003 – 0.009
Delay [ms]	0.632	0.255	1.140
Jitter [ms]	0.121 – 0.132	0.058 – 0.151	0.049 – 0.122
TCP			
Transferred payload [GB]	19.2 – 19.3	14.8 – 15.5	18.3 – 18.4
Bandwidth [Mbps]	275	212 – 221	262 – 263

In each test run, approximately 18 GB of the test data was transferred between the stations, both in TCP and UDP mode. The average transfer rate settled around 260 Mbps, which is high in the context of industrial applications. In an industrial environment, devices such as those from ABB or Siemens only use 100 Mbps links. Therefore, the achieved value is more than sufficient for optimal operation and communication of industrial systems. Tests show that the single “Management - Station” link achieved approximately 20% lower transmission speeds compared to the other two link types. However, it is important to stress that this reduced speed is not critical as it is a secondary link intended for testbed management and thus does not affect the overall system operation.

Furthermore, the value of the loss rate was monitored, which was doubtful in the order of a thousandths of a percent of the data transmitted. The main cause of this loss rate is the use of several network elements (e.g., switches), which may prioritize a more important type of data at certain times. The worst result was again achieved by the “Management - Station” connection, but again these values are values that do not prevent the testbed or its parts from running properly.

The last but not least important feature of the testbed is the communication delay between the stations. This is the time elapsed from the moment a request is sent from one device to the moment it is received by the response on the other device. This process may involve data transmission over various network protocols and transport over physical media such as cables or wireless networks. Delay can be affected by many factors such as distance between devices, network capacity, and the number of data that are transported. It is important to monitor and minimize delay, as it can affect the quality of service and applications transmitted over the network. From the measured results, it can be seen that the greatest delay is experienced during inter-station communication. This delay may be due to the higher load on the edge switch, which has to serve more than twenty devices simultaneously. However, it is important to emphasize that the measured values remain within a safe range without exceeding the maximum limit for optimal operation set at

FIGURE 10. Device response during data interface flooding.

3 ms, that is, the lowest set of values for message types according to IEC 61850-5 [62]. This includes, for example, the GOOSE protocol message. Delay variability values, also known as jitter, were monitored during the tests. These values oscillated between 0.05 and 0.15 ms. This result is considered excellent and cannot be considered a limiting factor in the operation of the testbed.

Additionally, the ability of the emulated station to process commands from the management server was tested under maximum load on the data network interface. In addition to the already tested throughput of the second interface, the main indicator was the response of the management interface. The following Figure 10 shows the course of the test, in which the data interface of the RPi device (eth0) was loaded with the maximum number of received data and the response of the second management interface (eth1) was measured. Red dashed lines indicate the beginning and end of the maximum load of the eth0 interface. The blue curve shows the measured response values. Although the response at maximum load increased by approximately 40%, except for the initial shock congestion, this level is sufficient for communication with the device. In the transmission system, the critical response limit may be when the power grid must respond to a change in power or load to ensure grid stability and security. In our case, this is the ability to change the device settings using the control interface. Thus, the boundary is not precisely defined, but it must not make communication between the management server and the emulated station completely impossible.

C. SCALABILITY TESTING

As part of the testing, a series of evaluations focused on the scalability of the testbed were conducted. These tests included a set of measurements, where each set consisted of three ten-minute tests aimed at maximizing the generation of operational data for TCP and UDP protocols across 1, 5, 10, 20, and 47 RPi devices. The measurements were carried out between the RPi devices and the OpenMUC server. Similarly, data generation for the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol and its secure TLS version was performed. The periodic message transmission interval was set to one second, and one and four instances were tested for each version. The test results are presented in Table 6.

The results indicate that the testbed can generate up to 10 Gbps (for TCP and UDP data). However, this is constrained by the hardware limitations of the communication links themselves (i.e., the 10 Gbps connection between the

TABLE 6. Scalability of testbed data generation.

Rpi	TCP [Mbps]	UDP [Mbps]	IEC 608750-5-104 [Kbps]	TLS 1.1 [Kbps]
1	261	266	53.60	97.01
5	1,305	1,331	268.00	485.27
10	2,604	2,655	535.81	969.30
20	5,180	5,276	1,067.43	1,936.90
47	9,874	9,931	2,512.61	4,558.81

OpenMUC server and the intermediate switch). In terms of scalability for generating IEC 60870-5-104 protocol data, it is possible to generate 1,833 ASDU messages per second (2.5 Mbps for the unsecured version and 4.5 Mbps for the secured version). This value can be further increased by adjusting the configuration of the emulation program beyond standard operation.

V. TESTBED APPLICATION

The network security testbed we have developed offers a wide range of application capabilities that are key to modern cybersecurity in the energy sector. This innovative tool provides an ideal environment for data generation, cybersecurity education in the energy sector, and equipment security testing.

A. DATA GENERATION

One of the key application elements of our testbed is the ability to generate near real-world data that can be used for predictive algorithms in energy network cybersecurity. Access to real data is often difficult due to security and corporate constraints, and this is where our generated data provides an alternative source of information for training and testing prediction models.

The devices to record and store network traffic are part of the Network Infrastructure section shown in Figure 4. The network elements that allow this are set up to mirror the communication directed to the recording device in the form of a NAS. The remaining network traffic is routed through ProfiShark 1G,⁹ which sends the recorded traffic to the same recording device via USB 3.0. Management is managed from the management station listed in Figure 4. All network traffic logs are stored in PCAP format and are time-stamped outside the name with when the log was started and from which device it was generated.

In addition to communication log, communication analysis is performed on a network probe we developed, built on the SCAPY¹⁰ library. The library allows parsing of network packets for standard application protocols such as HTTP, FTP, or DNS. Energy protocols are not implemented within the library, but thanks to a well-designed system, adding new parsers for other protocols is relatively easy. The library allows us to perform an almost real-time analysis of the communication there, visualizing it, and possibly filtering

⁹<https://www.profitap.com/profishark-1g/>

¹⁰<https://github.com/secdev/scapy>

FIGURE 11. Convolutional neural network normalized confusion matrix.

only the necessary packets or protocols. The probe is built on the Debian Linux distribution, making it easily portable. The only necessary elements are network interfaces and enough power to parse and filter the necessary traffic.

Actual data generation depends on the scenarios and devices used. It is thus possible to generate/emulate network traffic from one or more devices as required, and recording is limited by the available storage, which is limited to 4x 16TB in RAID 10, allowing up to 32TB of backed-up network traffic to be stored.

The testbed was utilized to create a dataset of secure communication for the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol using TLS, serving as the basis for an analysis employing convolutional neural networks. The goal of the analysis was to determine the operational state of the devices without knowledge of the encryption keys. The results demonstrated that it is possible to classify operational states to a limited extent based on message signatures, with the length of transmitted messages being a critical factor. The findings were visualized using a normalized confusion matrix, as shown in Figure 11, illustrating the achieved classification accuracy. The most frequent misclassifications occurred between states with similar messages, such as Overcurrent and Short Circuit. Nevertheless, the overall accuracy of correct classification exceeded 67%.

B. EDUCATION

In use, the testbed is related to the innovative educational tool BUTCA,¹¹ as shown in Figure 1. This is a comprehensive platform providing a controlled and secure space for learning in the field of cyber security. This platform incorporates a cyber-physical environment with various scenarios related

¹¹<https://butca.vut.cz/en/>

FIGURE 12. CTF IEC 60870-5-104 diagram.

to information technology, industry, and energy. BUTCA also offers live interactive scenarios that reflect current trends and technology challenges, including concepts such as IT/OT convergence, Industry 4.0, and the Internet of Things. BUTCA allows users to conduct training in a real-world environment and gain practical skills to combat modern cyber threats. One of the exceptional features of the platform is the wide range of customizable scenarios that can be tailored to the user's needs. In addition, users have the ability to create their own personalized scenarios at the user group level, providing flexibility and opening up space for creative cybersecurity education. BUTCA is a key learning tool that links theoretical knowledge with practical skills, contributing to the development of cybersecurity professionals.

Within our testbed, we have successfully implemented a wide range of industrial and energy protocols including IEC 61850, IEC 60870 and Modbus. For these protocols, we have created Capture the Flag (CTF) educational games that allow students and professionals to practice their cybersecurity skills in a fun way. We focus not only on the technical aspects, but also on real attack scenarios and defense strategies in the context of real devices that are part of our testbed. This innovative approach to teaching not only provides practical skills, but also prepares our students for the current challenges in industrial and power systems cybersecurity.

A CTF scenario was created for educational purposes. The topology and actual functioning of the testbed were used to create the scenario. The scenario aims to introduce the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol used, its features, and its capabilities. It comprises six basic parts illustrated in Figure 12. Each part comprises several sub-tasks that help understand the mentioned protocol and the remote control issues in general. Within a subtask, the learner is presented with a particular feature/capability, the understanding of which is always verified by a specific task on the issue. Each task contains a set of hints that help the subject understand the issue.

- *Introduction* - In the first part, the learner is introduced to the operation of the CTF and the issue of remote control of electrical substations using the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol.
- *General properties* - The second part focuses on the basic communication of IEC 60870, its different parts and the communication model supported by the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol.
- *Message structure* - The next part focuses on the actual structure of the data frame of the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol. The different parts of the APDU, the frame formats and their usage are introduced. The process of initiating and terminating a data transfer and the format of the ASDU data unit itself are also described.

- *Types of message* - The last educational part focuses on the detailed use of the different types of messages, including an introduction to all their options and uses. Last but not least, the timestamp used by the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol is discussed and explained graphically.
- *Final exercise* - The CTF concludes with an independent assignment to test the student's understanding of the subject. This assignment combines knowledge of the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol and the appropriate tools that students have been introduced to in previous assignments.
- *Control test* - At the end of the whole CTF, a control test was created. Its purpose is to test all the theoretical knowledge acquired so far about the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol.

The developed scenarios were also tested in an educational setting with students, enabling the verification of their practical applicability. Based on student feedback, it was found that they gained a better understanding of the subject matter. They deepened their theoretical knowledge through practical exercises, which helped them better comprehend real-world security incident scenarios. During the lessons, students also learned to analyze and address complex situations, enhancing their ability to critically evaluate problems in both cybersecurity and the operation of electrical systems.

C. SECURITY TESTING

Testbed offers a wide range of applications in information security education. Its design, modeling a real system layout, including real devices, allows to perform tests of cyber incidents that can significantly affect the running of a real system. Examples of such incidents include Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, Man-in-the-Middle (MiTM), certificate fraud, and others. However, the testbed not only tests cyber attacks, but also provides a suitable platform to examine and implement countermeasures associated with these threats.

With realistic simulations in the testbed, it is possible to conduct comprehensive tests that include cyber incidents and their follow-up and response. This allows students and information security professionals to gain practical skills in dealing with complex cyber situations and improves their ability to respond adequately to real-world security threats.

6) DDoS: We can simulate and execute DDoS attacks using testbed stations within our testbed. This capability allows us to create scenarios in which we add an additional station to the testbed that represents the attacker. This attacker station then attempts to exploit the hardware resources available from the compromised stations to disable essential system functionality.

In this way, we can closely examine and test the resistance of individual system components or connected production devices to DDoS attacks in a secure environment that faithfully simulates real cyber threats. This capability allows us to identify potential system weaknesses and develop and

test countermeasures to protect against these types of cyber-attacks effectively.

7) *MitM*: Within our testbed, we have the ability to simulate and analyze *MitM* attacks, where an attacker attempts to disable key functionality of a substation or directly impact production equipment by compromising routing equipment within the internal data network.

Through these attacks, we can thoroughly examine how our systems withstand these sophisticated attacks that target traffic manipulation and impact the integrity of communications. Simulating *MitM* attacks in a testbed allows us to identify potential security risks and develop effective countermeasures to protect key functionality of the substation and production facilities.

With the testbed created, we are able to simulate other methods of *MitM* attack, which uses TLS communication establishment on the secure version of IEC 60870-5-104 protocol. This sophisticated attack method allows an attacker to influence the data that are sent to the monitoring center, in our case to the OpenMUC server. In this way, we can examine and test the resilience of the system and individual devices to cyber threats that target the security mechanisms of establishing communication in a secure environment. Analyzing this version of the *MitM* attack allows us to identify possible weaknesses in protection and develop effective measures to prevent this kind of cyber risk. In addition, through this tutorial scenario, we can improve the log-traceback analysis capabilities.

8) *Application in Security Testing*: One of the significant uses of the BUTENET testbed is the evaluation of real industrial devices to identify security vulnerabilities. Testing real devices is conducted using a series of simulation-based tests. Each testing process is unique, as devices, even of the same type (e.g., RTU, IED), do not follow a standardized structure. These devices vary in terms of operating systems, firmware, and input/output configurations. The tested physical device is connected to BUTENET, which provides the necessary communication counterparts. BUTENET simulates various roles within the network, including a regular user, an attacker, and other essential elements. For instance, testing the security level of RTU units used in photovoltaic power plants can be structured into the following categories of tests:

- *Sustainable Design* - Sufficient hardware resource reserves; Management and reporting of system changes during updates and patches; Remote management of cryptographic credentials.
- *Cryptography* - Secure cryptographic algorithms; Secure cryptographic (pseudo-)random number generator; Secure storage of cryptographic credentials.
- *Communication Security* - Validation of protocol suite; Integration and use of network access management (firewall); Resistance to physical resource exhaustion.
- *Backup, Startup, and Updates* - Protection of integrity, authenticity, and non-repudiation during startup,

updates, and recovery; System protection against errors during startup, updates, and operation.

- *Support for Security Operations* - Authorization and access management within the system and user roles; Logging of security events.
- *System Hardening* - Use of only necessary software components; Use of only necessary hardware components; Regular system and software updates; Random access memory protection; Separation of security, communication, and process functions.

VI. DISCUSSION

One of the core parts of this paper was the analysis of testbeds, which are used to replace the fundamental infrastructure or part of it, and for example to allow simulation of various scenarios, data generation or security training. The extensive Table 1, was divided into four groups, which are discussed in the following.

From the analysis of the Realization group, which is shown in percentage in Figure 13, we found that the virtual/simulated testbeds are implemented the most. Virtual or simulated testbeds are not the most used in a design, security testing, or educational scenarios. In the field of energy, devices are costly. For this reason, virtualization or simulation software is mainly used for non-critical scenarios, which can give the user an approximation of the real system behavior. However, for testing real devices, for example, this is not the most suitable, as virtualization software usually cannot test all inputs, outputs and states of the device as if it were in a real environment. Physical testbeds are almost equally represented, which is insignificant in the energy sector. Due to the need for critical functionality and long-term durability, testing on physical testbeds is usually the most similar to real-world cases. The last representative, with almost half the representation of the others, is an emulated testbed. In the energy sector, these are usually not stand-alone testbeds, but are part of a physical testbed or an extension of a virtual/simulated testbed. However, these testbeds offer only the benefits of both other testbeds. Like the virtual/simulation ones, they usually offer simple reconfigurability of either binary or network interfaces. In terms of physical testbeds, they usually have real inputs and outputs that can be connected directly to the real environment. However, these devices usually do not achieve the same criteria, time or otherwise, so they cannot be used in the real world and are used more for testing.

From the analysis of the Protocols group, shown in percentage in Figure 14, the IEC 61850 standard has the most significant representation. Today, this standard is increasingly being deployed worldwide for communication within the electrical transmission and distribution network. Approximately one third of the standard less represented is DNP3, widely used in North America and Australia. With approximately half that, the IEC 6070 standard is represented in testbeds, specifically IEC 60870-5-104, which is very similar to DNP3. It is used primarily for communications

FIGURE 13. TAB Realization.

FIGURE 15. TAB Elements.

FIGURE 14. TAB Protocols.

within the energy sector in Europe, as it is more compliant with established criteria than DNP3. Another protocol with the exact representation in the testbeds mentioned is Modbus TCP. In most cases, this protocol is not used primarily for data transfer in power equipment, although it is represented in some cases as an alternative to the above protocols. It is a relatively old but still widely used protocol in all industries. Nowadays, it is on the decline in the energy sector and is mainly used for support systems associated with it. The latest protocol is the OPC UA, which represents just over 6%. This protocol is not as widely used in the power sector, although its variability makes it suitable for deployment in almost any system. The protocol transmits different protocols, for example, to a control center while preserving the format and structure of the data. Because of these characteristics, it is more widely represented in the industrial sector, where many proprietary protocols are found. In the analysis of communication protocols, most testbeds today focus on actual protocols for communication in the energy sector.

From the analysis of the Elements group, shown in percentage in Figure 15, the IED station communicating as a server station has the most significant representation. In most cases, these are sensing and protection devices, critical devices in the electrical station. MTUs or RTUs, which are second, with almost the exact representation, are essential for communicating with SCADA. The remaining four elements

achieve similar results of around 12%. The representation of the elements on the testbeds can be considered standard. The focus on protection and sensing devices is understandable given their importance. However, given the increasingly widespread use of remote control today, it would be good to include SCADA, which plays a significant role in the testing. Given their infrastructure, they may seem more invulnerable. This is due to the human factor, which is always considered one of the weakest links, and the increasing interconnection with other systems or remote access of operators to the system via the Internet. All these can be entry points for attackers nowadays.

From the analysis of the Purpose group, shown as a percentage in Figure 16, Security has the most significant representation with more than 55%. With all systems increasingly connected to the Internet, their potential vulnerability is increasing. Therefore, increasing security is a logical step, especially for systems that belong to critical infrastructure. The focus on data generation and simulation comes second with 30.51%. Data sets for various analyses or as training data for prediction algorithms are highly desirable. Most representatives of the energy sector are not very comfortable providing data. This is mainly due to confidentiality and know-how preservation. Education in communication and energy security was only represented in 13.56%, which we consider a poor result. Expertise in terms of communication or security is essential to mitigating potential threats. Trained personnel who have gone through various scenarios and are aware of security risks can react faster to potential incidents that may arise or prevent them.

In addition to analyzing testbeds, we highlighted the importance of testbeds as safe alternatives for simulating scenarios, addressing the challenges of testing in real operating conditions. This included discussing system criticality, risks of operational failures, and the need for careful planning to minimize impacts. We emphasized testbeds' role in protecting sensitive data and assets, ensuring system integrity, and providing alternative information sources when real operational data is inaccessible. Overall, we analyzed and explained our findings, underlining the significance of network security testbeds for cybersecurity research, development, and training.

FIGURE 16. TAB Purpose.

VII. CONCLUSION

The paper deals with testbeds in the field of electricity transmission and distribution system, where a detailed analysis of energy testbeds has been carried out, focusing on the areas of data generation/simulation, education, and security. We have designed, implemented, and tested our own testbed focusing on data communication in the power industry, which is easily extensible and application independent due to its structure. Application applicability is presented in this paper in the fields of data generation/simulation, data communication education, and cybersecurity. From the communication point of view, Testbed covers two key protocols in the field of data communication in the power industry – IEC 61850, IEC 60870, where data communication and device emulation is implemented from the Process Layer according to IEC 61850 to the SCADA monitoring center using IEC 60870-5-104.

While the current implementation of the testbed has proven its utility in areas such as data generation, cybersecurity training, and communication protocol validation, there are numerous opportunities for further enhancements and broader applications. Incorporating advanced machine learning algorithms could enable real-time threat detection and predictive maintenance, increasing the testbed’s usefulness for proactive system management. Algorithms could also be used to simulate more accurate and adaptive learning scenarios. The cellular 5G network is also used for some examples in the context of energy networks. At Brno University of Technology, we have our own small 5G network, which could be integrated into BUTENET and thus extended with new testing possibilities, e.g., delay or availability.

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